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On the role of present bias and biased price beliefs in household energy consumption

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ABSTRACT

The intermittency of energy billing may give rise to different biases or misperceptions, such that household energy demand deviates from its true optimum. This study investigates such deviations by linking variation in present-biased preferences and energy price beliefs to variation in energy consumed. Using both a survey and incentivized experiments, we gather measures of present bias as well as price beliefs, and observe participants' true electricity consumption. Our main finding is that participants with present bias are predicted to consume on average 9 to 10 percent more electricity than participants with time-consistent discounting. Our results further suggest that neither the true marginal electricity price nor the perceived marginal electricity price can predict electricity consumption. These findings raise doubt as to the effectiveness of classic price-based policies in reducing household energy consumption.

1. Introduction

With the overall aim of mitigating climate change, governmental policy seeks appropriate measures for reducing the greenhouse gas emissions associated with energy production. While such reductions are in principle possible through behavioral or technological changes in household energy consumption, a necessary condition is to understand the underlying drivers of energy demand (Allcott and Mullainathan, 2010). Motivated by the intermittent billing structure of energy, this study tests how present-biased preferences and biased price beliefs explain actual energy demand. Specifically, the research question we seek to answer is, "To what extent do present bias and energy price beliefs explain households' energy consumption?"

In contrast to other goods, which are consumed and paid for at the same point in time, energy consumption and payment are separated in time. Due to the intermittent billing structure of energy, costs are only paid in recurring billing cycles, while the benefits of consumption are experienced immediately. As a consequence, households face an intertemporal trade-off between immediate benefits and delayed payment. Furthermore, intermittent billing results in infrequent reminders about the energy price. Thus, households might be less able to recall the true price and form biased price beliefs.¹ Therefore, intermittent billing can induce: [1] present-biased discounting of future costs and [2] biased beliefs of energy prices.

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¹ While smart meters and in-home-displays might increase the ability to correctly recall the true energy price, only 8 percent of our sample have access to a smart meter. Further, households may misperceive how energy service demand maps into kilowatt-hours consumed. However, as identifying such a misperception requires knowing household's true energy service production function, this work focuses on price misperceptions.

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If a household is present-biased, it devalues the future electricity bill by both the standard exponential discounting parameter and by a present bias parameter. As a non-present-biased household merely engages in exponential discounting, this implies a greater devaluation of future costs by a present-biased household — hence, increased energy consumption. As a present-biased household would like to consume less energy itself *ex ante*, its consumption choice is time-inconsistent and is considered as an unintended overconsumption of energy.

If the household cannot recall the energy price it pays, the energy consumption decision will depend on household's energy price beliefs. If the perceived energy price deviates from the true energy price, the household will consume too much or too little, compared to a decision with unbiased beliefs, depending on the direction of the deviation. In the end, both for present bias and biased price beliefs, energy consumption may deviate from its true optimum — either because marginal costs are overly devalued or because marginal costs are misperceived.

However, there is little evidence on the extent to which present bias and biased energy price beliefs explain household energy consumption. To fill this gap, we run an incentivized survey for which we employ classic lab elicitation measures to a sample recruited to be representative of the German population.² In multiple decisions, we gather incentivized estimates of each participant's present bias and energy price beliefs. Further, because the survey was operated through face-to-face interviews, we are able to observe participants' true electricity consumption. Each participant was asked to show her last electricity bill to the interviewer. Thus, we are able to derive reliable estimates of each participant's kWh consumption, present bias and price beliefs. While controlling for a vast set of control variables, we link variation in present bias and price beliefs to variation in electricity consumed.

Our results show that present bias predicts a 9 to 10 percent increase in electricity consumption compared to participants who apply time-consistent discounting. This relationship is significant at the 5-percent level and robust to other specifications and including control variables. Importantly, the result remains robust on controlling for the energy efficiency of appliances, measured as age of appliances and equipment with energy-efficient light bulbs. This suggests a link between present bias and energy consumption, apart from the previously studied link between present bias and energy efficiency investments. Hence, we provide evidence consistent with present-biased energy consumption, due to the intertemporal trade-off between the consumption and billing of energy. By contrast, our results show that neither the true marginal price of electricity, nor the perceived marginal price explain variability in electricity consumption. This suggests either a near zero (perceived) price elasticity or households maximizing their utility from energy consumption with respect to another price construct than those covered in this study.

Taken together, our results raise doubt as to the effectiveness of classic price-based interventions in reducing electricity consumption. According to our correlations, households do not maximize their utility from energy consumption with respect to their true energy price, and devalue energy costs quasi-hyperbolically. As intermittent billing is one potential explanation of these correlations, changes in the billing structure, such as prepaid schemes,³ should be considered first. Such changes in the billing structure, which eradicate the lag between energy consumption and payment, might be promising tools for combating both the associated internality and externality, and therefore increase overall welfare.

This research contributes to three strands of literature. First, it contributes to the literature on intermittent billing, which examines inattention and information effects of intermittent billing (Gilbert and Zivin, 2014; Grubb and Osborne, 2015; Sexton, 2015; Wichman, 2017), and studies the effects of changes in billing schemes, such as automatic withdrawal of costs (Sexton, 2015), bill shock alerts (Grubb and Osborne, 2015), more frequent billing (Wichman, 2017) and prepaid meters (Jack and Smith, 2020). While none of these studies has investigated present bias arising from the intermittent billing structure of energy, the intermittent billing structure of credit cards has been found to induce present-biased discounting and overconsumption (Shui and Ausubel, 2005; Meier and Sprenger, 2010; Kuchler and Pagel, 2021).

Second, our research contributes to the literature on experiments eliciting households' preference parameters and correlating them to energy outcomes. Among this literature, Qiu et al. (2014), Newell and Siikamäki (2015), Bradford et al. (2017), Schleich et al. (2019), Heutel (2019) and Fischbacher et al. (2021) are closest to our own work. These studies correlate energy efficiency investments with individual risk preferences, time preferences and social preferences. Moreover, Bradford et al. (2017) and Fischbacher et al. (2021) consider stated energy consumption measures, such as summer temperature in the home. Studies based on stated electricity consumption rely on participants recalling their consumption correctly, and might thus suffer from recall bias. We add to this literature by correlating revealed electricity consumption with preference parameters. Methodologically, we contribute to the literature relating measures elicited from laboratory experiments to real-world behavior (Levitt and List, 2007; Falk and Heckman, 2009; Falk et al., 2018) by providing further evidence on the validity of lab measures in predicting real-world behavior.

Third, the literature suggests a relationship between an energy price literacy and energy consumption (Brounen et al., 2013; Blasch et al., 2017; Brent and Ward, 2019). In line with this research, Ito (2014), Wichman (2014) and Shaffer (2018) have shown that consumers do not react to marginal energy prices, but to average energy prices. Further, Jessoe and Rapson (2014) find that participants' price elasticity triples once price changes are combined with information provision. However, none of these studies elicited participants' own energy price beliefs in an incentivized manner. Using incentivized measures of one's own energy price beliefs, we contribute evidence on the relationship between perceived energy prices and energy consumption, as well as variance in price beliefs and energy consumption.

The following Section 2 describes our data gathering, in particular the measurement of energy consumption, present bias and price beliefs. Section 3 gives some summary statistics of our main variables, before Section 4 specifies the regression model we use for our correlations. Section 5 presents and discusses our results, and Section 6 concludes.

² According to Harrison and List (2004), this is classified as artefactual field experiment.

³ With prepaid schemes, the household first has to charge the electricity meter with some monetary amount before being able to consume energy. See for example, Jack and Smith (2020) on large reductions in electricity consumption under prepaid schemes.

2. Measurement and elicitation of data

Our experimental data is based on a survey conducted in Germany between December 2017 and January 2018, with 711 participants, implemented as computer-assisted face-to-face interviews (CAPI). For recruitment and executing interviews, we cooperated with the GMS Dr. Jung GmbH and the ARIS Umfrageforschung GmbH.

The selection of participants was quota-based. First, the number of participants per federal state and inhabitants per city were selected. Given these state and inhabitant quotas, a combined quota of age and gender was created. Thus, our sample was recruited to ensure representativeness of the German population given federal state, city inhabitants, and across age and gender combinations. Interviewers then contacted potential participants, asked for their interest to participate in the study and made an appointment for the interview. Appendix B displays a translated English version of the original survey instructions.

2.1. Electricity consumption

To observe the true past electricity consumption, participants were asked to show their electricity bill for the last contracting year to the interviewer.⁴ To avoid a large dropout rate when asking for the electricity bill, participants were informed about this requirement upon recruitment. As participants were not aware of the incentivized price belief questions at that point in time, there was no evident need for participants to check and remember their marginal electricity price.

Of the 711 conducted interviews, 554 participants indeed provided their last electricity bill. To account for the possibility that participants failed to correctly recall their electricity use (recall bias), we restrict the sample to these 554 participants, as the true electricity consumption and true marginal electricity price was only observed for them. The results are, however, robust towards using the full sample (see Table A.4) and there is no significant correlation between showing the electricity bill and present bias or price beliefs.

2.2. Present bias

To estimate present bias, we confront participants with three decision situations: [1] Trade-off between a lottery and a safe payment, [2] trade-off between a smaller payment today and a larger payment in one month, [3] trade-off between a smaller payment in one month and a larger payment in two months.⁵ Decisions are assumed to be made from maximizing intertemporal utility:

$$U_t = u_t + \beta \sum_{i=t+1}^T \delta^{i-t} u_i,$$

with flow utility $u_t = y_t^\alpha$ from the experimental payments y_t at time t .⁶ Thus, we assume quasi-hyperbolic discounting involving an exponential discounting parameter $\delta \leq 1$ and a present bias parameter $\beta \leq 1$ (Laibson, 1997). Due to the change in valuation of future utility once the present is involved, present bias induces time-inconsistent choices. The α -parameter measures risk preferences, a value of $\alpha < 1$ implies risk aversion, $\alpha = 1$ means risk neutrality and $\alpha > 1$ indicates risk-seeking behavior. We estimate the three parameters α , β and δ using the decisions situations [1], [2] and [3].

The three decision situations are modeled in three Multiple Price Lists (MPLs), each aimed at identifying one parameter. The first MPL is used to adjust choices of the second and third MPL for risk preferences (Andersen et al., 2008). Hence, in the first MPL, participants are asked to decide between a lottery with equal chances of winning 300 euros or 0 euros, and a safe payment (Falk et al., 2016; Koch and Nafziger, 2019), which increases in 31 decisions from 0 to 300 euros, in increments of 10 euros. The lottery was the same in all decisions. The second MPL models 31 decisions of either receiving 100 euros today or a larger amount in one month. Across the 31 decisions the later payment increases from 100 euros to 175 euros, in increments of 2.50 euros, while the earlier payment remains constant at 100 euros (Falk et al., 2016). The third MPL uses the same 31 monetary amounts with only the payment dates being shifted to the future (Coller and Williams, 1999). Hence, the decision was between receiving 100 euros in one month or a larger payment in two months.

We present the MPLs with the staircase method (e.g., Abdellaoui et al. (2008, 2011), Van De Kuilen and Wakker (2011), Falk et al. (2016), Haushofer et al. (2018), Schneider and Sutter (2020)), such that participants only had to make five consecutive decisions instead of 31. Yet, this method has been criticized for giving participants an incentive to answer strategically, in order to increase expected payments. However, such strategic choices have only been observed for experienced subjects (Harrison, 1986), as it requires participants to understand the structure of the subsequently offered payments — which is unlikely for our participants who comprise a sample selected to be representative of the German population, and thus most probably had no experience with the staircase method and these types of experiments.⁷

⁴ In our sample, 17 percent are on monthly, and 81 percent on yearly billing.

⁵ The three decision situations are questions W1, W4 and W5, respectively, in Appendix B.

⁶ This specification of flow utility builds on the assumption that participants directly consume the experimental payment on receipt, and do not smooth consumption from the payments over time (Cohen et al., 2020).

⁷ An investigation of raw choices revealed that we can rule out strategic choices for the first and second MPL. However, some participants might have exploited the staircase in the third MPL. We adjust for this possibility in the analysis (see Section 4).

In each decision of each MPL, participants indicate which payment option they prefer. Thus, for the first MPL, each time the participant chooses the lottery, the safe payment is increased in the subsequent decision, until the participant switches and prefers the safe payment. Conversely, if the participant prefers the safe payment, the safe payment is reduced in the subsequent decision, until the participant prefers the lottery. This structure is repeated in the second and third MPL. Whenever the participant prefers the earlier payment, the later amount is increased in the subsequent decision, and the later amount is decreased if the participant prefers the later payment.⁸ As decisions are consecutive, we do not allow for multiple switching points and thus avoid violations of the monotonic preferences assumption.

For MPL $j \in 1, 2, 3$, we assume indifference between the underlying payment options at the midpoint \bar{y}^j at which the participant switches. As an example for the second MPL, if the participant prefers 100 euros today over 105 euros in one month and 107.50 euros in one month over 100 euros today, we assume indifference between payment today and in one month at $\bar{y}^2 = 106.25$. Formally, indifference is given by:

$$0.5 \cdot 300^\alpha + 0.5 \cdot 0^\alpha = (\bar{y}^1)^\alpha \quad (1)$$

$$100^\alpha = \beta \delta \cdot (\bar{y}^2)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

$$\beta \delta \cdot 100^\alpha = \beta \delta^2 \cdot (\bar{y}^3)^\alpha. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (1) presents indifference for the first MPL. Both the lottery and the safe payment are paid immediately, so that no discounting is involved and participants trade-off the expected utility from the lottery with the utility from the safe payment. Eq. (2) gives the indifference equation of the second MPL. As this MPL involves a trade-off between a payment of 100 euros today and a larger payment in one month, the future payment is discounted by β and δ . Eq. (3) gives the indifference equation of the third MPL involving a trade-off between two future payments. Following [Schleich et al. \(2019\)](#) and [Brown and Kim \(2014\)](#), these three equations are jointly solved for the three parameters α , β and δ for each participant.

Intuitively, if the participant switches in the second and third MPL at the same monetary amount, that is $\bar{y}^2 = \bar{y}^3$, we measure $\beta = 1$. The participant makes time-consistent choices. If the participant switches in the second MPL at a higher amount than at the third MPL, i.e. $\bar{y}^2 > \bar{y}^3$, a higher payment is needed to compensate for forgone present utility. The participant is present-biased, $\beta < 1$. We speak of future bias if $\beta > 1$, i.e. less money is needed to compensate for forgone present utility compared to forgone future utility. We expect a participant with a $\beta < 1$ to discount future energy costs to a greater extent than a participant with $\beta = 1$, and thus to overconsume compared to a time-consistent discounting participant.

2.3. Price beliefs

We elicit participants' electricity price beliefs by using the quadratic scoring rule for continuous events as outlined by [Harrison et al. \(2017\)](#).⁹ First, we explained the German energy-pricing structure to participants. This structure encompasses a base price¹⁰, paid as a fixed amount, and a marginal price, which is constant for all kilowatt-hours consumed.

Then, for five price intervals, participants are asked to estimate the probability that their marginal price for the last contracting year was inside that interval. The five price intervals, in eurocents, are [8–14], [15–21], [22–28], [29–35], [36–42].¹¹ The probabilities for these five intervals are required to sum to 100 percent. Alternatively, participants could state a 100 percent probability that their electricity price is either lower than 8 eurocents or higher than 42.

Participants were informed that their payment depends on the precision of their estimation. With q_i being the stated probability for interval i , the participant received $20 - 20 \cdot q_i^2$ euros, if her true price was not within the interval, and $20 - 20 \cdot (1 - q_i)^2$ euros if her true price was within the interval. The true electricity price paid was observed through the electricity bill which was shown to the interviewer after this question. We obtain the perceived energy price $\mathbb{E}(p_b)$ and the variance in price beliefs $\sigma^2(p_b)$ by assuming a uniform distribution of price beliefs p_b within intervals, and discrete jumps between intervals.

If the perceived electricity price deviates from the true energy price, the participant misperceives her energy costs and may consume too much or too little compared to unbiased price beliefs. A larger variance in price beliefs indicates that the participant is less confident in her estimation. If numeraire utility is non-linear, the participant may counter risks from a larger variance in price beliefs with less energy consumption.

⁸ [Table A.1](#) displays the summary statistics of switching points. There are 11 participants who never switched in the second MPL and 2 additional participants who never switched in the third MPL. Because these 13 participants were not willing to forgo 100 euros a month earlier to receive 175 euros a month later, we exclude these participants. Further, we exclude 5 participants, who preferred the lottery when offered a safe payment of 290 euros. These excluded participants either did not understand the MPLs or did not trust the payments, as the resulting annual discounting rates and risk aversion parameters do not correspond to other estimates reported in the literature. Our results are however, robust to including these participants, as reported in [Table A.5](#).

⁹ [Harrison et al. \(2017\)](#) present an approach which recovers the mean of the true latent distribution without adjustment for risk preferences.

¹⁰ We observe the true base price from the electricity bill, but refrain from analyzing the relation between average prices and energy demand due to the pricing strategy of energy suppliers: As customers with higher consumption get offered contracts with lower base prices, causality between average prices and demand might run in both directions. Indeed, we observe a strong correlation between base price and consumption in our data.

¹¹ Cf. question W6 in [Appendix B](#). The price intervals are chosen such that the price estimations measured by [Blasch et al. \(2017\)](#) in a survey of households in Switzerland are largely covered.

2.4. Control variables

Preference measures serve as a first set of variables that we control for in the regressions. This comprises risk and time preferences, i.e. the continuous measures of α and δ as elicited from the MPLs, and as outlined in Section 2.2. We further control for environmental preferences, which were elicited as the average answer to seven statements based on the OECD Greening Household Behavior classification (OECD, 2014). In a second step, we control for characteristics of the house and of the household by including the number of persons living in the household, the number younger than eighteen, and categorical variables on the type and size of the dwelling. A third set of variables controls for socio-demographic characteristics of the participant. We observe age, gender, a categorical education variable, an indicator of whether the participant is employed, and a categorical variable describing the participant's income status.

In a fourth step, we include covariates to control for participant's energy efficiency investments. This covers categorical measures on the share of energy-efficient light bulbs, including LED, compact fluorescent bulbs or halogen bulbs, and on the age of the washing machine, refrigerator and stove in the dwelling.¹²

2.5. Incentives

The elicitation of present bias, risk and time preferences as well as price beliefs, was incentivized. In particular, each participant had a 3.5 percent chance that one of her decisions in the three MPLs plus one price interval question is chosen to be paid. The MPLs include high stake incentives of up to 300 euros. For the price beliefs, we used rather low stakes with a maximum of 20 euros.

After survey completion, a computerized random mechanism decided whether the participant was selected for payment and which decision was selected. Payment logistics included a money check, which could be redeemed at all bank institutions.¹³ If the first MPL was selected for payment, the interviewer gave a check on the monetary amount to the participant directly after the interview. If the participant chose the lottery in the selected decision, a computer determined the lottery outcome.

If the second MPL and the 'today' option was chosen, the interviewer gave the check directly to the participant. If the participant chose a delayed payment in the second MPL, or the third MPL was selected for payment, she received a check via mail on the chosen date.¹⁴ This payment procedure ensures constant transaction costs across time, as the check needed to be refunded at all dates. While we cannot completely rule out uncertainty about future payments, we undertook various measures to ensure trust in payments. First, the German mailing system is known for its reliability. According to the Federal Network Agency, of the 12.2 billion letters sent in 2018 in Germany, only around 1071 letters were reported as lost (Federal Network Agency, 2018, 2019). Second, participants knew how to contact the interviewer if payments did not arrive, as participants knew the interviewer's name, phone number and/or email address. Third, participants could contact our cooperation partners. Both the GMS Dr. Jung GmbH and the ARIS Umfrageforschung GmbH are certified to adhere to guidelines and standards of quality research. Hence, reported misconduct would be detrimental for both companies.

In total, 25 participants were paid an average amount of 188.76 euros, the minimum payment was 0 euros, the maximum payment was 339.60 euros.

3. Summary statistics

Table 1 gives the summary statistics of our main variables.¹⁵ The average monthly energy consumption is 276.71 kWh and the standard deviation 104.44. The lowest consumption is 83.5 kWh, the largest 676.25 kWh. These estimates compare quite favorably with the statistics provided by Frondel et al. (2015) for Germany. Accordingly, the average energy consumption we observe corresponds to the consumption of a two-person household.

The average present bias estimate is 1.13, whereas the median participant is a time-consistent discounter. This can be explained by the fact that our data includes some extreme future bias values (such as a $\beta = 12.30$), which raise the average estimate. Comparing our estimate to other studies is difficult, as elicitation methods and procedures vary. Our average β -value is however, larger than other estimates in the literature.

For instance, Andreoni et al. (2015) estimate an average $\beta = 0.99$ when employing the DMPL method. Bradford et al. (2017) estimate an average $\beta = 1.02$. Schleich et al. (2019) estimate an average value of $\beta = 1$, but also find a large share of participants to be future-biased. The meta-analysis of Imai et al. (2021) estimates a mean $\beta = 0.9964$ in studies using monetary rewards, which is not significantly different from one. Further, they note substantial heterogeneity across studies. As such, they find higher β -estimates in field studies, and if the payment is made by check. Imai et al. (2021) also identify publication bias in the form of overreporting present bias.

One major difference compared to other studies is that our design inhibited multiple switching points in the MPLs. Other studies may report fewer outlier values, because some of them either exclude participants with multiple switching points or impose an assumption about the 'true' switching point. Further, our delay of one month between immediate and future payment is

¹² While we do not know the energy efficiency of these appliances, we suspected the age to be easier for participants to answer, and to be correlated with energy efficiency.

¹³ We refrained from using cash due to the obstacles of coin-based payments.

¹⁴ See Vischer et al. (2013), on the same payment procedure implemented so as to incentivize decisions on money-earlier-or-later trade-offs in Germany.

¹⁵ Table A.2 gives the summary statistics of the control variables.

Table 1
Summary statistics of energy consumption and explanatory variables.

Variable	Average	Percentile					N
	[Std. dev.]	10th	25th	50th	75th	90th	
kWh	276.71 [104.44]	157.25	198.00	268.00	328.83	413	537
β	1.13 [0.90]	0.96	1.00	1.00	1.04	1.15	516
$\mathbb{E}(p_b) - p$	1.90 [6.68]	-4.91	-2.00	0.90	4.56	10.74	470
$\sigma^2(p_b)$	20.00 [24.58]	4.00	4.00	15.76	21.64	53.00	474

Note: Standard deviations in parentheses.

comparatively small (cf. the meta-analysis of Imai et al. (2021)). We have done so to minimize uncertainty about future payments. A higher degree of uncertainty on the other hand should lead to more present-biased choices. Thus, the short time delay in our set-up may explain the large fraction of future-biased participants (Sayman and Oncüler, 2009; Takeuchi, 2011). Finally, future bias is consistent with truth-revealing choices in the second MPL, but shifting to strategic choices exploiting the nature of the staircase method in the third MPL. Hence, although it is impossible to distinguish between true future-biased preferences and strategic misreporting, such pattern may provide another explanation of why our β -estimate is higher than observed in other studies.

With regard to misperceived energy prices, the deviation between perceived and true energy price exhibits a slight overestimation on average. The reason for finding only a slight misperception on average might be the design of the price intervals with the middle interval containing the true energy price for most households. The distribution however, shows both over- and underestimation of energy prices, with overestimations being more pronounced in the sample.

The average variance in price beliefs is 20.00, where a variance of 4 means that the participant chooses one interval with certainty, and a variance of 102 means that the participant places equal probabilities on all five intervals. Hence, participants believed that they had some idea about possible magnitudes of their energy price. We are not aware of other studies which elicited incentivized own energy price beliefs.

Table A.3 gives the distribution of energy price misperceptions conditional on present bias. The distribution is broadly similar across individuals with present bias, with time-consistent discounting and future bias. Hence, participants have no systematic bias over both domains, ruling out general confusion in responses.

4. Empirical strategy

To examine the relation between present bias and energy consumption, we define two indicator variables for either *PresentBias* (i.e. $\beta < 1$) or *FutureBias* (i.e. $\beta > 1$) (see also Ashraf et al. (2006) and Meier and Sprenger (2010)). Time-consistent discounting (i.e. $\beta = 1$) is the omitted category in the analysis. If the coefficient of the *PresentBias*-indicator is significant and positive, this would constitute evidence of present-biased participants overconsuming energy, as compared to time-consistent discounting participants. Further, the *FutureBias*-indicator absorbs participants who potentially exploited the staircase to that extent that they appear future-biased while actually being time-consistent or present-biased. Hence, the *FutureBias*-indicator allows us to exert control over substantially misreporting participants.¹⁶

If participants have biased energy price beliefs, their perceived energy price, instead of their true energy price, will influence energy consumption. Additionally, the variance in price beliefs may impact energy demand. Similar to Ito (2014), we include the true energy price p , the perceived energy price $\mathbb{E}(p_b)$ and the variance $\sigma^2(p_b)$ in price beliefs, simultaneously in one regression. This enables us to test a model of biased energy price beliefs against a model of full information. If the coefficient of the true energy price is insignificant, whereas the coefficient of the perceived energy price is significant, this would be evidence against a model of full information about prices. Both $\mathbb{E}(p_b)$ and p are logarithmized, so as to interpret them as (perceived) price elasticity. The variance $\sigma^2(p_b)$ is standardized for interpretive reasons to have a standard deviation of one across participants.

Hence, to investigate the relationship between energy consumption, present bias and price beliefs, we run the following regression:

$$\log(kWh_i) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \text{Present Bias}_i + \gamma_2 \text{Future Bias}_i + \gamma_3 \log(p_i) + \gamma_4 \log(\mathbb{E}(p_b)_i) + \gamma_5 \sigma_i^2(p_b) + \gamma_6 \mathbf{X}_i + \epsilon_i,$$

where i is the index for each individual observation, the outcome is the logarithm of each participant's monthly kilowatt-hour consumption and the coefficients are given by the γ -values. \mathbf{X} is a vector of control variables and ϵ is the error term.

We employ different robustness checks on our measures for present bias, price beliefs and electricity consumption. First, we use two alternative indicator variables for present and future bias, which are based on only comparing switching points in the second

¹⁶ In case of weak misreporting incentives, present-biased participants will still be correctly classified as present-biased.

Table 2
Regression results of electricity consumption on present bias and price beliefs.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)
<i>PresentBias</i>	0.123*** (0.0465)		0.165*** (0.0490)	0.158*** (0.0571)	0.0903*** (0.0337)	0.102** (0.0396)	0.0928** (0.0403)
<i>FutureBias</i>	0.0220 (0.0372)		0.0453 (0.0400)	0.0634 (0.0449)	0.0106 (0.0248)	0.0167 (0.0282)	0.00611 (0.0293)
$\log(p)$		-0.172 (0.284)	-0.196 (0.278)	-0.0325 (0.301)	-0.169 (0.208)	-0.113 (0.225)	-0.102 (0.230)
$\log(\mathbb{E}(p_b))$		0.0943 (0.1000)	0.104 (0.101)	0.0292 (0.110)	-0.0673 (0.0594)	-0.0866 (0.0664)	-0.0515 (0.0702)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$		-0.00369 (0.0190)	-0.00635 (0.0195)	-0.0129 (0.0207)	-0.00582 (0.0117)	-0.00285 (0.0127)	0.00244 (0.0136)
Control 1				X	X	X	X
Control 2					X	X	X
Control 3						X	X
Control 4							X
<i>N</i>	516	454	436	378	355	307	298
Adj. R^2	0.007	-0.004	0.013	0.006	0.715	0.686	0.680

Note: Control 1: Exponential discounting parameter, risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

and third MPL. A higher switching point ($SP_{higher} = 1$) in the second MPL than in the third MPL indicates present bias. A lower switching point ($SP_{lower} = 1$) indicates future bias. The same switching point in both MPLs will again be the omitted category.

Second, to adjust for the above discussed possibility of strategic misreporting, we repeat our analysis without the third MPL. While this inhibits us from identifying β , we can identify a parameter for short-term, or monthly, discounting.¹⁷ Following the argumentation of O'Donoghue and Rabin (2015), Kaur et al. (2015) and Shapiro (2005), this short-term discounting parameter captures impatience and is largely influenced by present bias. Hence, we are able to answer our research question also by correlating the short-term discount factor with household energy consumption.

Third, an alternative measure of the perceived energy price is gathered from a question which directly asked participants about the electricity price they think they paid. This direct question was also incentivized with the quadratic scoring rule.¹⁸ Fourth, we use the logarithm of electricity consumption, normalized by the number of household members, as an alternate outcome.

5. Results

Table 2 presents the regression results of participants' electricity consumption on *PresentBias*, *FutureBias*, the true electricity price paid p , the perceived electricity price $\mathbb{E}(p_b)$ and the variance in price beliefs $\sigma^2(p_b)$. In columns (4) to (7) different sets of control variables are subsequently added. The first main finding displayed in Table 2 is that present bias significantly positively correlates with electricity consumption.

According to column (1), participants with present bias are predicted to consume on average around 13 percent more electricity than individuals with time-consistent discounting. Accordingly, a t-test on equal kWh means of present-biased and non-present-biased participants can be rejected at the 5-percent level.¹⁹ When including the price misperceptions in specification (3), the estimate increases further and stays significant at the 1-percent level. This positive correlation between present bias and electricity consumption is robust to including measures for risk, time and environmental preferences (column (4)).

Only when including household and dwelling characteristics in column (5), the estimate decreases and predicts an effect of about 9 percent, but remains significant at the 1-percent level. Further, the Adjusted R^2 jumps to 0.72 when including this second set of control variables. Both is explained by the number of household members as well as the type and size of the dwelling being, unsurprisingly, highly predictive of energy consumption.²⁰ Since specifications (1) to (4) did not control for these household characteristics, the present bias coefficient was biased upwards. As reported in specification (6), the significance and size of the present bias coefficient then remains robust to including socio-demographic characteristics of the participant as additional covariates.

¹⁷ More details about the exact measurement of the short-term discount factor and summary statistics are given in Appendix A and Table A.9.

¹⁸ Cf. question W7, in Appendix B. The maximum possible payment was 20 euros, and the payment increased with the precision of the estimation. While the number of observations decreases to 455 with the direct question, we observe an overestimation of the true electricity price by around 3 eurocents on average. To distinguish between the perceived price from the intervals and the direct question, we use the index 2 whenever we refer to the direct question.

¹⁹ A Mann-Whitney test rejects the hypothesis of equal medians at the 5-percent level.

²⁰ See Table A.11 displaying coefficients and significance levels of the control variables. Overall, correlations are as expected and support the validity of our data.

This result is particularly remarkable given that specification (7) of Table 2 controls for energy-efficient investments. Due to the relation between present bias and energy efficiency investments on the one hand, and energy efficiency investments and energy consumption on the other hand, the coefficient decreases compared to specification (6), but remains significant at the 5-percent level. Participants with present bias are predicted to consume 9.7 percent more electricity than time-consistent discounting participants. Further, when testing the coefficient of present bias against the coefficient of future bias, equality of coefficients is rejected at the 5-percent level.

This robustness of the present bias estimate in specification (7) implies a relationship between present bias and energy consumption, when holding our measures of energy efficiency investments constant. This suggests that we observe a linkage between present bias and energy consumption beyond the investment channel already discussed in the literature (e.g., Gillingham and Palmer (2014), Bradford et al. (2017), Schleich et al. (2019)). While it is not possible to identify the causal effect of present bias on energy consumption, a likely explanation for the robust correlation we observe is the intermittent billing structure of energy, which causes present-biased participants to undervalue the future energy costs, and thus to overconsume.

Our second main finding is that neither the true electricity price nor the perceived electricity price significantly predict electricity consumption in any specification of Table 2. Further, the coefficient of the perceived energy price is not significantly different from the coefficient of the true energy price. This result is consistent with both participants having a price elasticity of almost zero, and participants making consumption choices with respect to a different misperception in energy prices than the one studied here.²¹

The results of Table 2 are robust across our various robustness checks. In specification (5) of Tables A.4–A.8, the present bias coefficient is significant at the 5-percent level and varies between a 9 and 10 percent increase in electricity consumption for present-biased participants. Further, results are robust to using the short-term discount factor as alternate measure of present bias. As Table A.10 (6) shows, a one standard deviation increase in δ^{short} , i.e. becoming more patient, predicts an about 3 percent decrease in consumption which is significant at the 5-percent level. This robustness also holds for the results on the true electricity price, the perceived electricity price and the variance in price beliefs. Throughout the different specifications and measures, neither the true price paid nor the price beliefs significantly explain electricity consumption.

6. Conclusion

Understanding the drivers of energy demand is crucial for policymakers to identify and implement appropriate measures for reducing energy consumption and accordingly contribute to lower carbon emissions. Motivated by the intermittent billing structure of energy, the aim of this study is to broaden our understanding of the extent to which present bias and price beliefs explain household energy consumption. Using a survey including an artefactual field experiment with a sample selected to be representative of the German population, we are able to link variation in measured present bias and energy price beliefs to variation in electricity consumption as observed from participant's electricity bill. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to elicit participants' energy price beliefs in an incentivized manner and to correlate preference parameters to revealed electricity consumption.

Our main result is the significant correlation between present bias and electricity consumption, which remains robust upon including control variables and across different robustness checks. Participants with present bias are predicted to consume on average 9 to 10 percent more electricity than participants with time-consistent discounting. Importantly, this result is robust to controlling for the energy efficiency level of appliances. This robustness is consistent with a link between present bias and energy consumption resulting from intermittent billing, beyond the previously discussed link between present bias and energy efficiency investments. Our second main finding is that neither the true electricity price nor the perceived electricity price can predict electricity consumption, which is consistent with participants having a near zero (perceived) price elasticity.

Although our results are correlational, they raise doubt as to the effectiveness of traditional price-based policies. Households seem to be insensitive to energy prices and, if exhibiting present bias, seem to undervalue energy costs. Hence, increasing price awareness and alleviating present bias should play an important role in designing energy policies.

Previously discussed in the literature are feedback systems, which have proven to largely increase price sensitivity (Houde et al., 2013; Jessoe and Rapson, 2014; Lynham et al., 2016). While feedback systems should be ineffective in reducing present bias per se, smart devices may be combined with additional features serving as commitment device. Prior literature has proposed goal-setting "nudges" as commitment device to help present-biased households following through energy-saving plans (Harding and Hsiaw, 2014). Yet, recent evidence raises skepticism towards the effectiveness of such goal-setting programs by finding a low technology adoption rate and null effects of the goal-setting treatment (Löschel et al., 2020).

Further, as we argue in favor of present-biased overconsumption due to intermittent billing, changes in the energy billing structure could be promising tools for improving household decision-making and for raising overall welfare. A recent research strand investigates the consequences of intermittent billing and potential policy solutions. For example, the results by Gilbert and Zivin (2014) and Wichman (2017) suggest that more frequent energy billing will contribute to increasing price awareness and saliency. However, only pay-as-you-go billing will alleviate present-biased discounting (Werthschulte, 2020). As an alternative, prepaid meters have shown to be effective in reducing consumption (Jack and Smith, 2020). Additional to increasing cost awareness, such a pay-ahead billing scheme introduces a trade-off between immediate costs and future benefits of consumption. Overall, this research on intermittent billing is an important avenue for an enhanced understanding of a differentiating feature of energy markets and deserves more attention in the future.

²¹ The literature provides support for low price elasticities. To mention just a few, Reiss and White (2005) estimate a price elasticity of -0.39 , Allcott (2011) estimates -0.1 , Deryugina et al. (2020) estimate -0.09 in the short-run and -0.27 in the long-run.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Tables

Summary statistics of control variables

Table A.2 gives the summary statistics of the control variables. The average participant exhibits an exponential discount factor of 0.79, which is comparable to the 0.791 reported by Heutel (2019). This average value is however lower compared to other estimates as for instance reported by Bradford et al. (2017) or Schleich et al. (2019). Potential reasons why estimates of this study deviate from estimates of other studies are discussed in Section 3. Further, the estimates itself are not the aim of this study. Rather, we seek to investigate how variation in estimates links to variation in electricity consumption.

The α -parameter confirms the common result of risk aversion. Its magnitude is in line with the estimates by Heutel (2019) and Schleich et al. (2019). Environmental preferences are on average weakly pro-environmentalist. The average answer is 'Agree' to seven pro-environmental statements.

The average participant lives in a single family home attached to other houses with two persons and no children. The type of dwelling is measured in 1 'A single family home detached from any other house', 2 'A single family home attached to one or more other houses', 3 'Apartment in a building with 2 to 5 flats' and 4 'Apartment in a building with 6 or more flats'. The size of the dwelling is classified in: 1 'Up to 42 m²', 2 '43–65 m²', 3 '66–90 m²', 4 '91–120 m²', 5 '121–200 m²', 6 'More than 200 m²'. The average size of dwelling category is '91–120 m²'.

Regarding socio-demographic characteristics, the average participant is 49 years old, the sample has an equal split of male and female participants and the average participant has a '10-year degree (Mittlere Reife)' as highest educational degree. The categories for education are: 1 'Below primary education', 2 'Primary education', 3 '9-year degree (Hauptschulabschluss)', 4 '10-year degree (Mittlere Reife)', 5 'University qualification (Abitur)', 6 'Bachelor or master', 7 'PhD'. About 54 percent of the sample is either full- or part-time employed, the other 46 percent are 'Long time not employed (more than 3 months)', 'Retired/pensioner', 'Student' or 'Other economically inactive person'. Participant's income status is measured in the categories: 1 'Finding it very difficult on present income', 2 'Finding it difficult on present income', 3 'Coping on present income', 4 'Living comfortably on present income'. The average income category is 'Coping on present income'.

The average participant has 'Most' light bulbs being energy-efficient. The alternative categories are: 1 'None', 2 'Some', 3 'About half', 4 'Most', 5 'All'. The categories for the age of oven and stove, washing machine, freezer and refrigerator are 1 'Up to 3 years old', 2 '4–10 years old', 3 'Older than 10 years'. All appliances are on average '4–10 years old'. There are 13 additional responses indicating not having a washing machine, coded as category 4.

Table A.1
Summary statistics of switching points.

Variable	Average	Percentile				
	[Std. dev.]	10th	25th	50th	75th	90th
SP_1	106.99 [73.52]	25.00	45.00	95.00	155.00	215.00
SP_2	130.16 [21.90]	101.25	113.75	128.75	138.75	168.75
SP_3	135.91 [21.83]	101.25	118.75	138.75	158.75	168.75

Note: SP_1 , SP_2 and SP_3 denote the switching points in the first, second and third multiple price list, respectively. The first list allowed for switching points between 5 and 305 euros, in increments of 10 euros. The second and third list allowed for switching points between 101.25 and 176.25 euros, in increments of 2.50 euros. Standard deviations in parentheses.

Table A.2
Summary statistics of control variables.

Variable	Average [Std. dev.]
Control 1	
δ	0.79 [0.20]
α	0.91 [1.06]
Environmental preferences	2.98 [0.26]
Control 2	
Number of household members	2.39 [1.24]
Number of children	0.39 [0.75]
Type of dwelling	2.19 [1.21]
Size of dwelling	3.50 [1.21]
Control 3	
Age	48.76 [18.82]
Female	0.50 [0.50]
Education	3.97 [1.21]
Employment	0.54 [0.50]
Income status	2.77 [0.79]
Control 4	
Share of energy-efficient lightning	3.66 [0.90]
Age stove and oven	1.75 [0.77]
Age washing machine	1.77 [0.76]
Age refrigerator and freezer	1.72 [0.75]

Note: Standard deviations in parentheses.

Short-term discounting

As additional robustness check we computed the discount factor implied by the first and second MPL only, denoted δ^{short} . Without the third MPL, we solved the following two equations for both α and δ^{short} :

$$(1) \quad 0.5 \cdot 300^\alpha + 0.5 \cdot 0^\alpha = (\bar{y}^1)^\alpha,$$

$$(2) \quad 100^\alpha = \delta^{short} \cdot (\bar{y}^2)^\alpha,$$

where \bar{y}^1 and \bar{y}^2 are the indifference amounts of the first and second MPL, respectively. The discount factor, δ^{short} , thus measures monthly, i.e. short-term, discounting.

While we cannot infer the β -parameter without the third MPL, we follow the argumentation of O'Donoghue and Rabin (2015), that "any noticeable short-term discounting is evidence of present bias" (p. 274, Lesson #3). O'Donoghue and Rabin (2015) argue that already small degrees of short-term impatience imply unreasonably large exponential discount rates on an annual basis. The

Table A.3
Distribution of bias in price beliefs conditional on present bias.

Price intervals:	Average	Percentile				
	[Std. dev.]	10th	25th	50th	75th	90th
$\mathbb{E}(p_b) - p \beta < 1$	1.42 [6.40]	-6.50	-2.13	0.95	5.05	10.02
$\mathbb{E}(p_b) - p \beta = 1$	1.88 [7.45]	-5.56	-2.27	0.65	3.96	12.15
$\mathbb{E}(p_b) - p \beta > 1$	1.93 [6.23]	-4.38	-1.81	0.73	4.53	10.21
Direct question:						
$\mathbb{E}(p_b)_2 - p \beta < 1$	2.14 [7.55]	-6.60	-2.27	1.98	7.00	11.98
$\mathbb{E}(p_b)_2 - p \beta = 1$	2.62 [8.31]	-6.14	-3.20	1.31	7.10	13.15
$\mathbb{E}(p_b)_2 - p \beta > 1$	2.62 [6.91]	-5.73	-1.78	1.30	6.41	11.75

Note: Standard deviations in parentheses.

Table A.4
Regression results of electricity consumption on present bias and price beliefs, including stated values.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)
<i>Present Bias</i>	0.132*** (0.0437)	0.116** (0.0516)	0.0766** (0.0301)	0.0844** (0.0356)	0.0816** (0.0368)
<i>Future Bias</i>	0.0570 (0.0373)	0.0612 (0.0414)	0.0212 (0.0243)	0.0306 (0.0280)	0.0277 (0.0287)
$\log(p)$	-0.168 (0.199)	-0.104 (0.217)	-0.0239 (0.145)	0.0519 (0.156)	0.0607 (0.160)
$\log(\mathbb{E}(p_b))$	0.0613 (0.0978)	0.00391 (0.108)	-0.0381 (0.0543)	-0.0573 (0.0586)	-0.0250 (0.0604)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$	-0.0129 (0.0179)	-0.0180 (0.0190)	-0.00551 (0.0113)	-0.00316 (0.0125)	0.00110 (0.0129)
Control 1		X	X	X	X
Control 2			X	X	X
Control 3				X	X
Control 4					X
<i>N</i>	522	455	432	379	369
Adj. R^2	0.007	0.004	0.689	0.663	0.657

Note: This table includes participants with unobserved electricity bill, i.e. with stated measures of electricity consumption and price. Control 1: Exponential discounting parameter, risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

authors make the example that a $\delta^{year} = 0.69$ is inconsistent with exponential discounting as such a δ^{year} implies that individuals care about their life ten years from now by a factor of 0.69 less than about their life nine years from now. Such an argumentation has also been put forward by Kaur et al. (2015) and Shapiro (2005) to identify present bias in their data. Shapiro (2005) interprets a $\delta^{year} = 0.23$ as evidence of present bias.

Table A.9 gives the distribution of δ^{short} . The mean estimated $\delta^{short} = 0.83$ for one-month discounting implies an annual discount factor of $\delta^{year} = 0.11$. Such a discount factor means that the average participant discounts utility five years from now by a factor of

Table A.5

Regression results of electricity consumption on present bias and price beliefs, including MPL outliers.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)
<i>Present Bias</i>	0.161*** (0.0466)	0.157*** (0.0552)	0.0842*** (0.0316)	0.0959*** (0.0366)	0.0932** (0.0374)
<i>Future Bias</i>	0.0452 (0.0393)	0.0670 (0.0438)	0.0115 (0.0244)	0.0168 (0.0278)	0.00749 (0.0285)
$\log(p)$	-0.229 (0.274)	-0.0511 (0.300)	-0.185 (0.207)	-0.131 (0.224)	-0.124 (0.229)
$\log(\mathbb{E}(p_b))$	0.0889 (0.0990)	0.0255 (0.110)	-0.0674 (0.0579)	-0.0824 (0.0640)	-0.0423 (0.0672)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$	-0.00537 (0.0190)	-0.0114 (0.0201)	-0.00414 (0.0114)	-0.000530 (0.0122)	0.00492 (0.0131)
Control 1		X	X	X	X
Control 2			X	X	X
Control 3				X	X
Control 4					X
<i>N</i>	450	390	367	319	309
Adj. R^2	0.013	0.005	0.716	0.687	0.681

Note: This table includes 5 participants who did not switch in the first MPL until being offered a safe payment of 300 euros, and 12 participants who never switched in the second or third MPL. Control 1: Exponential discounting parameter, risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

Table A.6

Regression results of electricity consumption on price beliefs and present bias, measured from the switching points in the MPLs.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)
SP_{higher}	0.152*** (0.0508)	0.148** (0.0577)	0.0931*** (0.0339)	0.0978** (0.0394)	0.0899** (0.0404)
SP_{lower}	0.0396 (0.0395)	0.0561 (0.0438)	0.00854 (0.0242)	0.0122 (0.0277)	0.00209 (0.0289)
$\log(p)$	-0.173 (0.280)	-0.0304 (0.302)	-0.169 (0.209)	-0.106 (0.226)	-0.0967 (0.231)
$\log(\mathbb{E}(p_b))$	0.116 (0.101)	0.0354 (0.110)	-0.0642 (0.0597)	-0.0830 (0.0669)	-0.0477 (0.0706)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$	-0.00568 (0.0195)	-0.0115 (0.0208)	-0.00467 (0.0116)	-0.00288 (0.0127)	0.00260 (0.0136)
Control 1		X	X	X	X
Control 2			X	X	X
Control 3				X	X
Control 4					X
<i>N</i>	439	378	355	307	298
Adj. R^2	0.009	0.004	0.716	0.686	0.679

Note: Present bias (SP_{higher}) and future bias (SP_{lower}) are defined by comparing switching points in the second and third MPL. Control 1: Exponential discounting parameter, risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

Table A.7

Regression results of electricity consumption on present bias and price beliefs using direct question.

	(1) log(kWh)	(2) log(kWh)	(3) log(kWh)	(4) log(kWh)	(5) log(kWh)
<i>Present Bias</i>	0.165*** (0.0512)	0.162*** (0.0588)	0.0856** (0.0334)	0.100** (0.0386)	0.0933** (0.0389)
<i>Future Bias</i>	0.0399 (0.0408)	0.0675 (0.0451)	0.00846 (0.0255)	0.0167 (0.0296)	0.00862 (0.0301)
<i>log(p)</i>	-0.219 (0.283)	-0.00827 (0.303)	-0.145 (0.212)	-0.0574 (0.243)	-0.0534 (0.242)
<i>log(E(p_b)₂)</i>	0.150** (0.0762)	0.0544 (0.0785)	-0.0348 (0.0455)	-0.0725 (0.0528)	-0.0472 (0.0567)
Control 1		X	X	X	X
Control 2			X	X	X
Control 3				X	X
Control 4					X
<i>N</i>	429	374	352	303	293
Adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.020	0.009	0.713	0.686	0.685

Note: The direct question is used as measure of the perceived energy price. Control 1: Exponential discounting parameter, risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

Table A.8

Regression results of per-capita electricity consumption on present bias and price beliefs.

	(1) log(kWh/n)	(2) log(kWh/n)	(3) log(kWh/n)	(4) log(kWh/n)	(5) log(kWh/n)
<i>Present Bias</i>	0.0770* (0.0396)	0.0911** (0.0414)	0.0683** (0.0336)	0.0972** (0.0394)	0.0989** (0.0400)
<i>Future Bias</i>	0.00276 (0.0339)	0.00949 (0.0360)	0.0306 (0.0277)	0.0448 (0.0314)	0.0408 (0.0326)
<i>log(p)</i>	-0.0520 (0.274)	0.0276 (0.293)	-0.175 (0.222)	-0.139 (0.246)	-0.125 (0.260)
<i>log(E(p_b))</i>	-0.102 (0.0851)	-0.150* (0.0905)	-0.0930 (0.0642)	-0.127* (0.0689)	-0.110 (0.0764)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$	0.000751 (0.0143)	0.00528 (0.0153)	0.00882 (0.0113)	0.00869 (0.0126)	0.0108 (0.0139)
Control 1		X	X	X	X
Control 2			X	X	X
Control 3				X	X
Control 4					X
<i>N</i>	436	378	355	307	298
Adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.000	0.003	0.504	0.496	0.482

Note: The outcome variable is the logarithm of monthly kilowatt-hour consumption divided by the number of persons in the household (consumption per capita). Control 1: Exponential discounting parameter, risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

0.000016. Following the arguments above, such an annual discount rate is neither in line with existing literature nor human sense, but can be well explained by both present bias and exponential discounting. For example, a $\delta^{short} = 0.83$ is perfectly compatible with masking the product of $\beta = 0.84$ and $\delta = 0.99$. Thus, δ^{short} captures short-term impatience and is largely influenced by present bias. Table A.10 gives the regression results including δ^{short} .

Table A.9
Summary statistics of short-term discounting δ^{short} .

Variable	Average	Percentile					N
	[Std. dev.]	10th	25th	50th	75th	90th	
δ^{short}	0.83 [0.18]	0.61	0.75	0.88	0.95	0.99	518

Note: Standard deviations in parentheses.

Table A.10
Regression results of electricity consumption on short-term discounting and price beliefs.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)	log(kWh)
$z_{\delta^{short}}$	-0.0319* (0.0181)	-0.0339* (0.0194)	-0.0454* (0.0237)	-0.0289** (0.0118)	-0.0305** (0.0135)	-0.0323** (0.0142)
$\log(p)$		-0.184 (0.285)	-0.0442 (0.311)	-0.167 (0.212)	-0.107 (0.230)	-0.104 (0.231)
$\log(\mathbb{E}(p))$		0.106 (0.102)	0.0380 (0.110)	-0.0683 (0.0600)	-0.0801 (0.0669)	-0.0438 (0.0707)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$		-0.00698 (0.0197)	-0.0129 (0.0209)	-0.00541 (0.0117)	-0.00336 (0.0126)	0.00201 (0.0134)
Control 1			X	X	X	X
Control 2				X	X	X
Control 3					X	X
Control 4						X
N	518	438	380	357	309	300
Adj. R^2	0.003	0.001	-0.002	0.712	0.682	0.676

Note: The short-term discounting parameter δ^{short} is standardized across observation to have a zero mean and standard deviation of one. The standardized measure is denoted $z_{\delta^{short}}$. Control 1: Risk preferences, environmental preferences. Control 2: Number of household members, number of children, type of dwelling, size of dwelling. Control 3: Age, gender, education, employment, income status. Control 4: Energy-efficient lightning, age of oven, washing machine, refrigerator. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

Table A.11
Regression results of electricity consumption on present bias and price beliefs as displayed in Table 2 (7), including control variable coefficients.

	(1) log(kWh)
<i>Present Bias</i>	0.0928** (0.0403)
<i>Future Bias</i>	0.00611 (0.0293)
$\log(p)$	-0.102 (0.230)
$\log(\mathbb{E}(p_b))$	-0.0515 (0.0702)
$\sigma^2(p_b)$	0.00245 (0.0136)
Control 1	
Exponential discounting parameter δ	-0.0959 (0.0924)
Risk preferences α	-0.0211 (0.0156)
Environmental preferences	-0.0794 (0.0692)
Control 2	
Number of household members	0.192*** (0.0231)
Number of children	-0.0323 (0.0293)
Type dwelling: Attached single family home	0.0161 (0.0351)
Type dwelling: Apartment in building with 2-5 flats	-0.235*** (0.0521)
Type dwelling: Apartment in building with 6+ flats	-0.258*** (0.0389)
Size dwelling: '43m ² - 65m ² '	0.177* (0.101)
Size dwelling: '66m ² - 90m ² '	0.277*** (0.102)
Size dwelling: '91m ² - 120m ² '	0.270** (0.111)
Size dwelling: '121m ² - 200m ² '	0.355*** (0.115)
Size dwelling: 'More than 200m ² '	0.315** (0.125)
Control 3	
Age	-0.000646 (0.000883)
Female	-0.00487 (0.0250)
Primary education	-0.0581 (0.182)
9-year degree	-0.125* (0.0639)
10-year degree	-0.123* (0.0630)

(continued on next page)

Table A.11 (continued).

	(1) log(kWh)
University qualification	-0.142** (0.0709)
Bachelor or Master	-0.0931 (0.109)
PhD	-0.136* (0.0803)
Employed	0.0187 (0.0322)
Finding it difficult on present income	0.109* (0.0604)
Coping on present income	0.0535 (0.0489)
Living comfortably on present income	0.0603 (0.0635)
Control 4	
'Some' bulbs are LED	-0.0518 (0.0857)
'About half' bulbs are LED	0.0263 (0.0813)
'Most' bulbs are LED	-0.0425 (0.0822)
'All' bulbs are LED	0.0316 (0.0788)
Age oven and stove: '4–10 years old'	0.00604 (0.0304)
Age oven and stove: 'Older than 10 years'	-0.0396 (0.0376)
Age washing machine: '4–10 years old'	0.0322 (0.0276)
Age washing machine: 'Older than 10 years'	0.0809* (0.0474)
Age washing machine: 'Do not have'	0.00559 (0.0760)
Age refrigerator and freezer: '4–10 years old'	-0.00790 (0.0303)
Age refrigerator and freezer: 'Older than 10 years'	-0.0198 (0.0324)
N	298
Adj. R ²	0.680

Note: This table resembles Table 2 (7) in the main text, but includes coefficients and significance levels of the different control variables. α and δ are defined in Section 2.2. The omitted base categories of the categorical variables are: for type of dwelling 'A single family home detached from any other house', for size of dwelling 'Up to 42m²', for education 'Below primary education', for income status 'Finding it very difficult on present income', for energy-efficient lightning 'None', for the age of appliances 'Up to 3 years old'. More details on the control variables are given below Table A.1. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Significance levels: * : $p < 0.10$, ** : $p < 0.05$, *** : $p < 0.01$.

Appendix B. Supplementary material

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2021.102500>.

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